

1 **TLR adapter function by TASL and UNC93B1 distinguishes the KIR2DL3^{hi} killer cell fraction.**

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7 We describe here unique TLR adapter function associated with KIR receptor expression on natural killer (NK) cells. UNC93B1 and the TLR adapter TASL defined the transcriptome of killer cells expressing high levels of KIR2DL3 ('KIR2DL3^{hi}'). TLR3 and SLC15A4 segregated with the 'KIR2DL3^{lo}' fraction instead.

8 Citations

9 1. Heinz, L.X., Lee, J., Kapoor, U., Kartnig, F., Sedlyarov, V., Papakostas, K., César-Razquin, A.,
10 Essletzichler, P., Goldmann, U., Stefanovic, A. and Bigenzahn, J.W., 2020. TASL is the
11 SLC15A4-associated adaptor for IRF5 activation by TLR7–9. *Nature*, 581(7808), pp.316-322.